

white crystals ($\text{Me}_2\text{CO}-\text{C}_8\text{H}_{18}$), m.p. $61-2^\circ$. The ir, pmr and mass spectra identified it as n-octacosyl acetate (M^+ 452) and further confirmed by co-tlc, m.m.p. of its hydrolysed product, octacosanol, m.p. $84-5^\circ$ with an authentic sample.

The petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) fraction afforded a white solid, m.p. $90-91^\circ$. The infrared spectrum revealed it a long chain aliphatic acid. The mass spectrum of the mixture showed⁹ prominent peaks at m/e 424, 396, 381, 353, 325, 297, 73, 60, 57, 55, 43 and 41. The peaks at m/e 60 (base) and 73 are diagnostic of unbranched long chain fatty acids. Thus, the mass at m/e 424 and 396 are the molecular ion peaks corresponding to n-hexacosanoic acid (relative abundance 86.4%) and n-octacosanoic acid (13.6%) respectively. The identity of the compounds was further confirmed by gc of their methyl esters (CH_3N_2) followed by mass spectrometric analysis.

The alcoholic extract of defatted stem bark, after separating KCl, yielded glucose, rhamnose, sucrose and starch (identified by pc in the usual manner).

The chlorine content of the stem bark was determined by the standard method⁹ and found to be $0.92 \pm 0.01\%$.

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Commercial Utilisation of Local Variety *Dioscorea prazeri* for the Production of Diosgenin

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DIOSCOREA prazeri Prain and Burk grows abundantly in Darjeeling terai, Jalpaiguri and Malda districts in West Bengal¹, but its use as raw material for the isolation of diosgenin upto the desired limit of purity is not easy because a good percentage of interfering materials lead to the isolation of impure diosgenin². The existing technologies³⁻⁵ fail to produce the desired quality of diosgenin from this species while they work well for the other varieties of *Dioscorea*. The following improved technique can be successfully utilised for the isolation of diosgenin having high degree of purity even in a large scale basis from *D. prazeri*.

Isolation of diosgenin: Dry *D. prazeri* powder was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) for 6 h. The resulting defatted mass was hydrolysed with 6 N HCl for 8 h at boiling temperature and then extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) for 8 h. The crude product was crystallised from methanol to yield pure diosgenin.

Results and Discussion

The results of the process are given in Tables 1-5.

TABLE 1—PRESENCE OF FATTY AND WAXY MATERIALS IN *D. prazeri*

Expt. no.	Weight of <i>D. prazeri</i> powder kg	Weight of defatted <i>D. prazeri</i> powder kg	Weight of fatty and waxy mass g	Average % fatty mass removed
1.	1.200	1.181	19	
2.	1.300	1.279	21	
3.	1.390	1.360	20	1.66
4.	1.420	1.395	25	
5.	1.692	1.661	31	

TABLE 2—RECOVERY OF SOLVENT FROM DEFATTED MASS OF *D. prazeri*

Expt. no.	Amount of plant material kg	Volume of solvent kept absorbed by powdered plant material ml	Volume of solvent recovered ml	Recovery %	Average % recovery of solvent
1.	1.181	1 027.0	955.1	93	
2.	1.279	1 112.2	1 023.2	92	
3.	1.360	1 182.6	1 064.3	90	90
4.	1.395	1 213.0	1 067.4	88	
5.	1.661	1 444.3	1 256.5	87	

TABLE 3—AMOUNT OF HYDROLYSED DEFATTED MASS OF *D. prazeri*

Expt. no.	Weight of defatted mass taken for hydrolysis kg	Weight of hydrolysed defatted mass g	Decrease in weight of the mass g	Average % reduction in weight of defatted mass after hydrolysis
1.	1.181	354.3	826.7	70
2.	1.279	383.7	895.8	
3.	1.360	408.0	953.0	
4.	1.395	418.5	976.5	
5.	1.661	498.8	1 162.7	

TABLE 4—RECOVERY OF SOLVENT FROM HYDROLYSED MASS AFTER EXTRACTION OF DIOSGENIN

Expt. no.	Amount of hydrolysed mass g	Volume of solvent kept absorb by the mass ml	Volume of solvent recovered ml	Recovery %	Average % recovery of solvent
1.	354.3	687.7	586.7	92	88
2.	383.7	690.7	621.6	90	
3.	408.0	734.4	646.3	88	
4.	418.5	753.3	662.9	88	
5.	498.8	896.9	771.3	86	

TABLE 5—YIELD OF DIOSGENIN FROM HYDROLYSED *D. prazeri*

Expt. no.	Amount of the <i>D. prazeri</i> taken kg	Amount of hydrolysed <i>D. prazeri</i> g	Amount of crude diosgenin obtained g	Amount of pure diosgenin obtained g	Recovery %
1.	1.200	354.3	10.8	8.4	80
2.	1.300	383.7	11.7	9.2	
3.	1.380	408.0	15.2	12.3	
4.	1.490	418.5	14.2	11.4	
5.	1.692	498.3	20.3	16.6	

Survey of literature^{2,6} shows that the diosgenin content in *D. prazeri* is highly variable (2–4.5%). But during the aforesaid experiments the authors have found that it ranges from 1 to 1.2% in the locally available plant material. The technique described have got 75–80% nett working efficiency in producing pure diosgenin (m.p. 192°). The technique is not only superior to the other methods but also more economically beneficial if it can work with *D. prazeri* having higher percentage of diosgenin content.

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